

DEVELOPING A FINANCIAL WELLNESS PROGRAM FOR LIBRARIANS

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ABSTRACT

Financial wellness is essential for employee well-being and productivity. This study assesses the financial wellness of university librarians and develops a Financial Wellness Program to address identified gaps. Findings indicate strengths in bill payment, debt awareness, and financial security but highlight challenges in budgeting, saving, and financial literacy, particularly in credit management. To improve financial well-being, the proposed program includes financial literacy workshops, financial counseling, and an Employee Assistance Program (EAP). These initiatives aim to enhance financial knowledge, provide personalized guidance, and support employees facing financial hardships. The study recommends regular workshops, expanded financial counseling, strengthened EAP services, fostering financial wellness culture, and continuous program evaluation. Implementing these strategies is expected to reduce financial stress, improve decision-making, and enhance job satisfaction, ultimately benefiting both employees and the organization.

Keywords: *Financial wellness, employee financial wellness program, financial literacy, budgeting, savings, credit management, productivity.*

INTRODUCTION

Financial wellness refers to an individual's ability to effectively manage their financial life. It involves developing healthy money habits, setting realistic financial goals, and taking actionable steps toward achieving them—all with the ultimate aim of enhancing overall well-being (Adams, 2025).

According to Adams (2023), financial wellness can be understood through four key categories: short-term finances, long-term finances, present financial freedom, and future financial freedom.

Managing short-term finances involves creating a budget, adhering to it, and gradually increasing income. Consulting a financial professional is an effective strategy for establishing financial stability in the short term.

Managing long-term finances requires allocating funds for savings and investments to achieve future financial goals. Strengthening financial wellness today supports objectives such as homeownership and retirement planning. Liersch, head of advice and planning at Wells Fargo Wealth & Investment Management, recommends that individuals collaborate with a financial advisor, spouse, or family member to review assets and liabilities as part of long-term financial planning.

Improving present financial freedom entails gaining control over short-term finances, fostering confidence in financial management.

Achieving future financial freedom necessitates consistent efforts toward long-term financial goals, with retirement planning serving as a fundamental component.

Literature Review

The COVID-19 pandemic significantly impacted financial security, leading to heightened uncertainty among employees (Rist, 2023). Malkowska (2022) further highlights that the crisis resulted in a loss of financial security among employees, which, in turn, led to decreased productivity. This decline in performance also affected employers, who faced additional costs related to reduced efficiency. As a result, organizations must take proactive steps to support employees' financial wellness.

Financial wellness is a key component of overall employee well-being. As organizations increasingly recognize its importance, they understand that employees' financial health directly influences job performance and productivity. Fouché and Manyapelo (2020) argue that employers must be equipped with the knowledge to assess and address employees' financial wellness effectively. Similarly, Pyron and Pettus (2019) emphasize that financial stress negatively affects work performance, further reinforcing the need for workplace financial wellness initiatives.

One of the key findings from Fidelity research was that workers are experiencing higher levels of financial stress, which can negatively impact their productivity at work (Karim, 2022). Consequently, Rosando (2024) emphasized that providing financial wellness resources is not merely a benefit but a strategic necessity for organizations aiming to retain talent and enhance productivity.

A study on the state of employee financial wellness (2023) highlighted key findings, including the need for organizations to better understand and support their employees' financial needs. The study also revealed that fewer than half of organizations currently have a financial wellness program in place.

Employee Financial Wellness Programs (EFWPs) are an emerging practice that can promote financial inclusion by improving access to financial services for workers with low and moderate incomes (LMI) (Despard et al., 2020).

Lamb (2023) emphasized the growing importance of financial wellness as a key employee benefit, highlighting the impact of financial stress on productivity and the advantages of providing financial education in the workplace. He stressed the need for employers to implement financial literacy programs, demonstrating their benefits for both employees and organizations while aligning with the trend of modernizing payroll processes to enhance the employee experience.

For this reason, the researcher felt compelled to conduct a thorough investigation to assess the financial wellness of university librarians, with the goal of developing a financial wellness program tailored to their needs.

Research Questions

The study aims to assess the financial wellness of librarians at the University of the Assumption with the view of drafting a financial wellness program. Specifically, it aims to answer the following:

1. How may the financial wellness of library staff be assessed and described?
2. What activities may be proposed for library staff to improve their financial wellness?
3. What financial literacy program can possibly be formulated for the improvement of library staff's wellness?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative research design, specifically the descriptive method. Quantitative research is a systematic approach to gathering and analyzing data that focuses on numerical measurements and statistical analysis. It aims to quantify

observations and gather measurable data to formulate facts and uncover patterns in research (Creswell, 2014). The descriptive method, a type of quantitative research, aims to accurately portray the characteristics of a particular individual, situation, or group. It focuses on describing and summarizing existing conditions, behaviors, or phenomena (Trochim, 2006).

Respondents

The respondents of this study comprised all library staff of the University of the Assumption from the grade school, junior high school, and the Cinense Library.

Research Instrument

The 2018 Personal Wellness Assessment, which encompasses eight dimensions of wellness, served as the primary data-gathering tool, with a specific focus on the financial wellness dimension.

Data Collection

Questionnaires were administered to all librarians at the University of the Assumption.

Data Analysis

Data were tabulated, calculated, and statistically analyzed. Frequency counts, percentage distributions, means, and standard deviations were used to discuss and interpret the findings.

Ethical Considerations

The study prioritized the ethical treatment of participants, ensuring that their rights and well-being were safeguarded throughout the research process. Participation was entirely voluntary and free of charge, with potential respondents receiving a clear explanation of the program's benefits before agreeing to participate. Only librarians who provided informed consent were included in the study.

To maintain privacy and confidentiality, all personal and financial information shared by participants was handled with strict discretion. Identifiable data were anonymized, and access was restricted to authorized personnel only.

To address potential conflicts of interest and ensure objective assessments, a professional counselor conducted the personal financial evaluations. Additionally, an independent evaluator was engaged to assess the program's effectiveness and provide unbiased feedback. These measures ensured the integrity and fairness of the study while upholding ethical research standards.

RESULTS

Based on the assessment results on Table 1, respondents demonstrate a moderate level of financial wellness with a score of 30 out of 40. Strengths include responsible bill payment, awareness of debt and interest rates, and practicing good financial security measures. Areas for improvement include budgeting, saving regularly, and enhancing financial literacy, particularly regarding credit card usage and building credit.

Table 1
Financial Dimension of Wellness

FINANCIAL	Scores
I am able to set and stick to a budget each month so I don't run out of money.	3
I know my total amount of debt and interest rates.	4
I pay my credits, tuition/fees and other bills on time.	4
I know about the different sources of financial aid that I am eligible for and apply when I am able.	3
I have a savings account and save money regularly.	3
I know my credit score.	3
I keep my financial information safe by using secure password, PINs and dual authentication.	4
I feel good about my current and future financial situation.	3
I check my bank statements/accounts each month.	3
I understand how to build credit and use credit cards wisely.	3
TOTAL	30

Table 2 outlines a proposed activity under the financial dimension of wellness. The suggested initiatives include financial literacy workshops focused on budgeting and saving, employee assistance programs that provide financial counseling, and retirement planning seminars to help employees secure their financial future.

Table 2
Proposed Activities for Financial Wellness

Dimension of Wellness	Proposed Activities
Financial	Financial literacy workshops on budgeting and saving, employee assistance programs with financial counseling, retirement planning seminars.

Table 3 presents the Financial Wellness Program, which is designed to enhance the overall well-being of library staff by addressing financial challenges through structured activities and resources. The program includes financial literacy workshops, financial

counseling, and an employee assistance program (EAP), all aimed at improving employees' financial stability and reducing financial stress.

The Financial Literacy Workshops focus on key financial topics such as budgeting, saving, debt management, and retirement planning. These sessions equip employees with essential money management skills to make informed financial decisions.

The Financial Counseling component provides employees with access to confidential financial advisors or counselors who can offer personalized guidance on managing finances, setting financial goals, and handling financial difficulties.

Additionally, the Employee Assistance Program (EAP) serves as a safety net for employees facing financial emergencies or hardship situations, offering resources and support to help them navigate financial crises.

Table 3

Financial Well Librarian: A Proposed Financial Wellness Program

Financial Wellness	To enhance the overall well-being of library staff by addressing each dimension of wellness through targeted activities and resources.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial Literacy Workshops: Offer education on budgeting, saving, debt management, and retirement planning. • Financial Counseling: Provide access to confidential financial advisors or counselors. • Employee Assistance Program: Offer resources for financial emergencies or hardship situations.
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DISCUSSION

The assessment results indicate that respondents demonstrate a moderate level of financial wellness, scoring 30 out of 40. While employees exhibit strengths in responsible bill payments, debt awareness, and financial security measures, areas needing improvement include budgeting, saving regularly, and enhancing financial literacy, particularly in credit card usage and credit building. These findings highlight the need for targeted financial wellness initiatives to address the identified gaps.

To address these concerns, a set of proposed activities under the financial dimension of wellness has been outlined. The suggested initiatives focus on financial literacy workshops, financial counseling, and employee assistance program (EAP). These activities are designed to enhance employees' financial knowledge, equip them with practical money management skills, and provide the necessary support to help them achieve financial stability.

Building on this, a structured Financial Wellness Program has been developed to enhance the overall well-being of library staff by addressing financial challenges through education and support services. The program integrates three key components:

Financial Literacy Workshops – These sessions focus on essential financial topics such as budgeting, saving, debt management, and retirement planning, providing employees with the tools needed to make informed financial decisions.

Financial Counseling – Employees gain confidential access to financial advisors or counselors who offer personalized guidance on managing finances, setting financial goals, and overcoming financial challenges.

Employee Assistance Program (EAP) – This program serves as a safety net for employees facing financial emergencies or hardships, offering financial resources and crisis support to ensure their stability.

Conclusions

The assessment results indicate that employees demonstrate a moderate level of financial wellness, with strengths in bill payment, debt awareness, and financial security. However, challenges remain in budgeting, regular saving, and financial literacy, particularly concerning credit card usage and credit building. These findings highlight the need for structured financial wellness initiatives to address these areas for improvement.

The proposed financial wellness program, which includes financial literacy workshops, financial counseling, and an employee assistance program (EAP), provides a comprehensive approach to enhancing employees' financial well-being. Implementing this program is expected to reduce financial stress, improve financial decision-making, and enhance overall job satisfaction and productivity.

Recommendations

To ensure the effectiveness of the financial wellness program, the following recommendations are proposed:

Implement Regular Financial Literacy Workshops. Conduct periodic training sessions on budgeting, saving, debt management, and retirement planning to enhance employees' financial knowledge and decision-making skills.

Provide Access to Financial Counseling Services. Establish partnerships with financial advisors or counselors to offer confidential financial consultations tailored to employees' specific needs.

Strengthen the Employee Assistance Program (EAP). Expand the EAP services to include financial aid resources, emergency financial assistance, and crisis management support.

Encourage a Culture of Financial Wellness. Integrate financial well-being discussions into workplace programs to promote an open and supportive environment for financial growth.

Evaluate Program Effectiveness. Conduct regular assessments and feedback sessions to measure the impact of the financial wellness initiatives and make necessary adjustments for continuous improvement.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to ethical research principles to ensure the protection and well-being of all participants. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents before their participation, and they were given the freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without consequences. The anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents were strictly maintained, ensuring that no identifying information was disclosed. Measures were taken to safeguard the well-being of participants throughout the research process. Additionally, no conflicts of interest existed in the conduct of this study. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, and all sources were properly credited. The interpretation of findings remained unbiased, and the results were used solely for research purposes to contribute to the field of workplace wellness for librarians.

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